

Proposal for a new seismic hazard zonation map for Greece

Kyriazis Pitilakis – Aristotle University, Thessaloniki, Greece, kpitilak@civil.auth.gr

Evi Riga – Aristotle University, Thessaloniki, Greece, eviriga@civil.auth.gr

Stefania Apostolaki – Aristotle University, Thessaloniki, Greece, aestefan@civil.auth.gr

Abstract: The current seismic hazard zonation map in Greece, published in 2003 following the catastrophic earthquakes that hit Greece between 1978 and 2001, includes three seismic hazard zones with PGA ranging between 0.16g and 0.36g. In the last two decades, a significant progress has been made towards the improvement of the seismic hazard maps worldwide using fully probabilistic models. At European level, in December 2021 the European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20 was released, built upon recently compiled and fully cross-border harmonized datasets, information and models. One of the main goals of ESHM20 was to interact with the subcommittee responsible for the ongoing revision of Eurocode 8 within the European Committee for Standardization (CEN). Within this context, in this paper we propose a new seismic hazard zonation map for Greece, based on the results of ESHM20, for potential inclusion in the Greek National Annex which will accompany the revised Eurocode 8. The herein proposed zonation for rock sites according to EC8 with $V_s > 800$ m/s, includes four zones with PGA values ranging between 0.12g and 0.37g. For each zone the parameters $S_{a,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$ are provided, which are the two seismic hazard parameters adopted in the revised Eurocode 8.

Keywords: seismic hazard map, Greece, ESHM20, Eurocode 8

1. Introduction

Greece is the most seismically active region in Europe, and therefore the European country with the highest seismic hazard. The current seismic hazard zonation map for Greece, in force since 2003, is essentially an update of the zonation of the 1992 seismic code NEAK, and came as a consequence of the many catastrophic earthquakes that hit Greece in the period between 1978 and 2001 (e.g. M_s 6.4 Thessaloniki event in 1978, M_s 6.2 Kalamata in 1986, M_s 6.6 Kozani-Grevena and M_s 6.4 Aigio events in 1995, M_s 5.9 Athens event in 1999). This map was prepared jointly by the five main seismological research centers of Greece (University of Athens, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Geodynamic Institute of the National Observatory of Athens, Institute of Engineering Seismology and Earthquake Engineering and University of Patras) and includes three seismic hazard zones with peak ground acceleration values of 0.16 g, 0.24 g and 0.36 g (Fig. 1). No site-specific amplification factors are proposed in this version of the code.

In the last two decades, a lot of efforts have been made to improve the seismic hazard maps worldwide, adopting the results of probabilistic seismic hazard analyses. In Italy, a new probabilistic seismic hazard model, MPS19, was developed in 2019 by the Seismic Hazard Center of the Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV), taking into account a large amount of recent data and methods (Meletti et al., 2021). This model will be taken into consideration to update the Italian building code (NTC, 2018), which is currently based on the previous MPS04 seismic hazard model. In Turkey, updated probabilistic seismic hazard maps were developed with the support of the Disaster and Emergency Management Authority of Turkey (AFAD) (Akkar et al., 2017), in line with the development of the new seismic design code. In USA the national seismic hazard model

was updated in 2017-2018 with the incorporation of an updated seismicity catalogue, new ground motion models and basin terms for long periods (Petersen et al., 2020). In New Zealand, a revision project for the National Seismic Hazard Model has recently commenced, expected to deliver a revised seismic hazard map in an open-source computational library, a web tool to make the results of the model openly available as well as peer-reviewed documentation by August 2022. Regarding similar efforts at European level, in December 2021 the European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20 (Danciu et al., 2021) was released, developed within the EU funded project “Seismology and Earthquake Engineering Research Infrastructure Alliance for Europe” (SERA). This model, which is fully probabilistic, is essentially an update of the previous ESHM13 (Woessner et al., 2013), proposed in the framework of SHARE project (Giardini et al., 2013), and was built upon recently compiled and fully cross-border harmonized datasets (i.e., earthquake catalogues, active faults, ground shaking recordings), information (tectonic and geological) and models (seismogenic sources, ground shaking). The source data, input models and output of ESHM20 are online available at the portal of the European Facilities for Earthquake Hazard and Risk (www.hazard.EFEHR.org), which will maintain and further develop the model in collaboration with the GEM Foundation and the European Plate Observing System (EPOS).

Fig. 1 – Current seismic hazard zonation map for Greece (EAK, 2003)

Apart from the strictly scientific objectives of ESHM20, including the development of the actual updated and harmonized model and the support of the development of the European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20, Crowley et al., 2021), one of the main objectives was to interact with CEN/TC250/SC8, i.e., the subcommittee of national experts that is responsible for the development of Eurocode 8 within the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), as well as with key experts at national level, to ensure the correct information and timely implementation of the ESHM20, and extend the output to serve additional engineering requirements as part of the update and revision of Eurocode 8. Within this context, ESHM20 produced two hazard maps for rock conditions and for the two seismic hazard parameters of the new under revision Eurocode 8 - Part1, $S_{a,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$, which will be included in an Annex of the revised Eurocode 8, as an “acceptable representation of the seismic hazard in Europe for the return period of 475 years”.

However, the spectral acceleration maps to be used for design will still be provided by the relevant Authorities or the National Annex of each country. Within this context, the present work aims to propose a new seismic hazard zonation map for Greece, based on the results of ESHM20, for potential inclusion in the Greek National Annex which will accompany the revised Eurocode 8.

2. Evolution of seismic hazard zonation in Greece

The first seismic zonation map for Greece was published in 1939 in the journal “Technical Chronicles”, no 184 and was later reformed and included in the book by Roussopoulos (1949; 1956). The 1956 version of this map divides the Greek territory into 5 seismic zones with different seismic coefficients for each zone and for three types of soil conditions (soft, medium and hard soil), ranging between 0.01 g and 0.16 g. This zonation formed the basis for the first seismic code in Greece, published in 1959, which included three seismic zones and three soil categories, with seismic coefficients ranging from 0.04 g to 0.16 g. The 1984 revision of the seismic code did not affect the seismic zonation. The next seismic code, NEAK, which was regulated in 1992 and implemented in 1995, included four seismic zones with peak ground acceleration (PGA) ranging between 0.12 g and 0.36 g, regardless of the soil type. This seismic zonation map was slightly modified in 1995 to upgrade some cities to a higher seismic zone. The same zonation was adopted by the 2000 version of the code (EAK, 2000). Finally, in the 2003 version of EAK, the zone of 0.12 g was removed and three seismic zones remained with PGA between 0.16 g and 0.36 g, again regardless soil conditions and site amplification. The evolution of the seismic zonation in Greece is shown schematically in Fig. 2. The 2003 zonation of EAK is currently used as seismic map for rock-site conditions in the Greek National Annex of Eurocode 8 (CEN, 2004), while it has not been designed for this purpose. This means that the PGA value of each zone is multiplied by an amplification factor (soil factor S) dependent on the soil type, which was not the case in NEAK and EAK, where it was assumed that all sites located within the same zone have the same PGA for seismic design regardless of soil type. We should stress that the evolution of the seismic codes in Greece included not only the update of the seismic zonation as described above, but also significant changes in the methods of analyses and in the practices of seismic design.

Fig. 2 – Evolution of seismic hazard zonation in Greece

2. ESHM20 in the revision of EC8

The seismic hazard results of ESHM20 are provided at a grid covering the whole Europe and Turkey, with grid points equally spaced at 0.1 to 0.1 degrees, resulting in a total number of 97920 grid points including points offshore. For each grid point, the following output is provided: (a) hazard curves depicting the mean, median (50th) and four percentiles (5th, 16th, 84th and 95th) for specified intensity measures (PGA and spectral acceleration values at periods in the range of 0.05s to 5s); (b) Uniform Hazard Spectra (UHS) depicting the mean, median (50th) and four percentiles (5th, 16th, 84th and 95th) for five mean return periods T_m (i.e. 50, 475, 975, 2500 and 5000 years). In addition, hazard maps are provided for all intensity measure types and for all return periods.

As a result of the interaction of ESHM20 with CEN/TC250/SC8 for the development of the revised Eurocode 8, ESHM20 further provides for each grid point the two seismic hazard parameters used in the revised Eurocode 8 to anchor the horizontal elastic response spectra for rock conditions ($V_{s,30} > 800\text{m/s}$), namely $S_{\alpha,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$. $S_{\alpha,475}$ is the maximum response spectral acceleration (5% damping) corresponding to the constant acceleration range of the horizontal elastic response spectrum, while $S_{\beta,475}$ is the spectral acceleration (5% damping) at the vibration period $T_{\beta}=1$ s of the horizontal elastic response spectrum, both specified on site category A (rock site conditions) and for a return period of 475 years. $S_{\alpha,475}$ is linked with peak ground acceleration at rock site conditions for $T=475$ years, which is the seismic hazard parameter used in the current EC8 (denoted as a_{gR}) through parameter F_A , defined as the ratio of $S_{\alpha,475}$ to PGA and set equal to 2.5 in the absence of specific seismic hazard studies. On the other hand, $S_{\beta,475}$ introduces a new concept in the definition of EC8 elastic response spectra, which are additionally anchored to a vibration period representative for flexible structures, T_{β} , equal to 1 s unless otherwise specified. The $S_{\beta,475}$ parameter strongly influences the shape of the normalized response spectrum, as it affects the corner period T_C , which specifies the end of the constant spectral acceleration branch of the spectrum. The definition of the elastic response spectra in the revised EC8 with two parameters ($S_{\alpha,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$) is in line with the recent developments in the definition of seismic actions, including NEHRP seismic code provisions in the U.S.A. (FEMA, 2015).

For each grid point, $S_{\alpha,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$ were computed from the respective UHS for a mean return period T_m equal to 475 years. For the computation of $S_{\alpha,475}$, an averaging formula was applied over the values of the UHS for selected spectral values around the spectral period which provided the maximum value in the UHS. This means that $S_{\alpha,475}$ is not the peak value of the UHS, and thus the spectral acceleration at the plateau of the of the elastic code spectrum (and consequently PGA) is a sort of “effective” value rather than the absolute maximum. For $S_{\beta,475}$ the spectral value of the UHS for $T=1$ s was adopted. Mean and median values, as the 5th, 16th, 84th and 95th percentiles are provided by ESHM20 for both $S_{\alpha,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$. The spatial distribution of the median (50th percentile) and the 84th percentile for $S_{\alpha,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$ is shown in Fig. 3.

3. Proposed seismic zonation map

The new seismic hazard zonation proposed for Greece in this study is based on the output of ESHM20 for the grid points located in the territory of Greece, and more specifically on the median $S_{\alpha,475}$ values (Fig. 3a), following the recommendations resulting from the discussions between ESHM20 and the respective Ad Hoc Group of CEN/TC250/SC8 on Seismic Hazard.

Fig. 3 – Spatial distribution of a) median $S_{\alpha,475}$, b) 84th percentile of $S_{\alpha,475}$, c) median $S_{\beta,475}$ and d) 84th percentile of $S_{\beta,475}$ derived from ESHM20 for Greece.

To ensure smooth transfer of the new zonation in engineering practice as well as to the community and the economy, the proposed zonation should not differentiate dramatically from the current seismic map (Fig. 1). For this reason, the herein proposed zonation includes four seismic zones, i.e., only one additional zone has been added with respect to the current seismic map.

The methodology adopted for the development of the new seismic hazard map can be summarized as follows: First, we applied the Natural Breaks (Jenks, 1967) algorithm, available in the open-source GIS software QGIS to break down the $S_{\alpha,475}$ values of the Greek territory into four classes. This algorithm tries to find natural groupings of data to create classes so that the variance between individual classes is maximized, while the variance within each class is minimized. At this stage we used two different datasets: one corresponding only to the terrestrial grid points of the Greek territory (Fig. 4a) and one also including the offshore grid points of the Greek territory and a number of grid points located in the bordering countries at the northern and eastern cross border region of Greece (Fig. 4b). It is evident that the consideration of the additional grid points does not affect the resulting zonation of Greece, so in the following we used only the terrestrial grid points located in Greece (Fig. 4a). The borders of the zones defined by the points in each of the classes shown in Fig. 4 were then smoothed, so that they do not cross large urban areas with more than 2,000 buildings, while specific areas belonging in the same administrative units were harmonized to simplify the

application of the seismic regulations in these regions. The seismic zonation map resulting from the methodology described above is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4 – Median $S_{\alpha,475}$ values derived from ESHM20 for Greece. Classification based on the natural breaks (Jenks, 1967) method considering (a) only the terrestrial points of ESHM20 and (b) the terrestrial and the offshore grid points of ESHM20.

Fig. 5 – Proposed seismic hazard map

To gain a better insight on the distribution of the $S_{\alpha,475}$ values at the different zones, and solemnly for checking in further detail the uncertainties involved, we divided each zone in a number of subzones and for each subzone we calculated the average $S_{\alpha,475}$ as well as the range between the maximum and the minimum values of median $S_{\alpha,475}$ (Fig. 6). The calculated median values and the scatter confirmed the reasonable decision of four zones as depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 6 – Average and range of median $S_{\alpha,475}$ (right) at the subzones of the proposed seismic hazard map (left)

As each zone has to be associated with a single $S_{\alpha,475}$ value, for each one of the four proposed zones of Fig. 5 we calculated the average $S_{\alpha,475}$ over the points located within each zone, as well as the respective average PGA ($=S_{\alpha,475}/2.5$). The obtained values are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean $S_{\alpha,475}$, PGA and $S_{\beta,475}$ for the seismic zones of the proposed seismic hazard map

Seismic Zone	Proposed zonation - $S_{\alpha,475}$ (g)	Proposed zonation - PGA (g)	Proposed zonation - $S_{\beta,475}$ (g)
Zone 1	0.31	0.12	0.13
Zone 2	0.50	0.20	0.16
Zone 3	0.71	0.28	0.24
Zone 4	0.92	0.37	0.34

Regarding the $S_{\beta,475}$ parameter, which as was mentioned previously significantly affects the shape of the normalized elastic response spectrum, the use of higher percentiles than the 50th (median) was explored. The use of higher percentiles allows for a better accounting of the epistemic uncertainties of the ground motion models and the seismogenic sources, which in the case of Greece are very high due to the very complex seismo-tectonic context of the region. An example of adopting different percentile for $S_{\beta,475}$ is shown in Fig. 6, which compares for the proposed zone 3 of Fig. 5 the elastic response spectra for soil type A (rock site conditions) based on the revision of Eurocode 8 (CEN, 2021) using the average $S_{\beta,475}$ value over the grid points located in this zone obtained (a) from the median $S_{\beta,475}$ map shown in Fig. 3c (orange dashed line in Fig. 7) and (b) from the 84th percentile $S_{\beta,475}$ map shown in Fig. 3d (orange solid line in Fig. 7). The elastic response spectra for soil type A of the current EC8 as well as EAK 2003 are also included in Fig. 7 for the sake of comparison. We observe that the use of the median $S_{\beta,475}$ results in a spectrum with a significantly narrower branch of constant acceleration (plateau) compared to most seismic codes in force, which in its turn would result in a significant decrease of seismic force for buildings with spectral periods higher than 0.4s, including many typical 3-8-storey buildings in Greece. For this reason, we decided to adopt the use of the 84th percentile $S_{\beta,475}$, which results in spectrum shapes which are more consistent with the current practice, respecting at the same time the seismogenic and ground motion features of the region.

The proposed $S_{\beta,475}$ values for the four zones of Fig. 5 were therefore calculated as the average of the 84th percentile $S_{\beta,475}$ over the points located within each zone, and are also included in Table 1.

Fig. 7 – Elastic response spectra for rock site conditions based on the revision of Eurocode 8 (CEN, 2021) considering the median $S_{\beta,475}$ map (orange dashed line) and the 84th percentile $S_{\beta,475}$ map (orange solid line), and elastic response spectra of the current EC8 (black solid line) and of the EAK2003 (black dotted line)

5. Comparisons with the current seismic zonation

In Fig. 8 we compare the proposed seismic zonation map of Fig. 5 with the current seismic zonation map of Greece (EAK 2003, Fig. 1) in terms of peak ground acceleration (PGA). The highest discrepancies are observed in western Peloponnese and in the regions around the gulf of Corinth (red and orange symbols in Fig. 8), which in the proposed map are in zone 4 with $PGA=0.37g$, while in the EAK 2003 zonation they are in zone 2 ($PGA=0.24g$) or zone 1 ($PGA=0.16g$). On the contrary, in northern Greece and in the islands of the Cyclades, the PGA according to the herein proposed zonation is lower than the one in EAK. For the remaining territory of Greece, the discrepancies are limited.

Fig. 8 – Spatial distribution of the difference between the PGA values of the herein proposed seismic hazard map and the PGA values of EAK 2003

Similar conclusions can be drawn by the comparison of Fig. 9a and 9b, illustrating the EAK 2003 and the proposed zonation with the respective PGA values, indicating also the main cities in Greece. Considering that in EAK 2003 the PGA values are actually for

average soil and site conditions without considering any extra amplification as proposed in the current EC8, in Fig. 9c we provide the design PGA values in the four zones with an average amplification factor for $S_{a,475}$ equal to 1.2, which corresponds to soil conditions of medium stiffness and moderate seismicity, i.e. PGA values for rock conditions of the order of 0.25g.

Fig. 9 – Spatial distribution of PGA according to (a) EAK 2003, (b) the herein proposed seismic hazard map for reference rock and (c) the herein proposed seismic hazard map for soil amplification factor $S=1.2$

6. Conclusions

We propose a new seismic hazard zonation map for Greece, based on the results of the newly released European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20. The herein proposed zonation for rock sites for reference rock site conditions includes four zones with PGA values ranging between 0.12g and 0.37g. For each zone the parameters $S_{a,475}$ and $S_{\beta,475}$ are provided, which are the two seismic hazard parameters adopted in the revised Eurocode 8. Compared with the current seismic zonation in force in Greece (EAK 2003), the peak ground acceleration values based on the herein proposed zonation are higher for western Peloponnese and in the regions around the gulf of Corinth, and lower for northern Greece and the islands of the Cyclades, while for the remaining territory of Greece, the discrepancies are limited. The proposed seismic zonation map could be considered for

potential inclusion in the Greek National Annex which will accompany the revised Eurocode 8.

Acknowledgements

This study was funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreements No 730900 (SERA) and No 952300 (ISTOS). We would like to thank Laurentiu Danciu for his support on ESHM20 and all members of the SC8-AHG2 'Seismic hazard' for the fruitful discussions that took place within the WG.

References

- Akkar, S., Azak, T., Çan, T., Çeken, U., Demircioğlu, M. B., Duman, T., Ergintav, S., Kadirioğlu, F. T., Kalafat, D., Kale, Ö., Kartal, R. F., Kılıç, T., Özalp, S., Altuncu, S. P., Şeşetyan, K., Tekin, S., Yakut, A., Yılmaz, M. T., Yüçemen, M. S., & Zülfikar, Ö. (2007). Updated Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Maps for Turkey. 2475.
- CEN European Committee for Standardization (2004). Eurocode 8: Design of structures for earthquake resistance - Part 1: General rules, seismic actions and rules for buildings, European Standard EN 1998-1:2004. Brussels, Belgium.
- CEN European Committee for Standardization (CEN/TC250/SC8) (2021). Working draft of EN 1998-1-1:2021, Eurocode 8: Earthquake resistance design of structures — Part 1-1: General rules and seismic action. October 2021.
- Crowley, H., Dabbeek J., Despotaki, V., Rodrigues, D., Martins, L., Silva, V., Romão, X., Pereira, N., Weatherill, G., Danciu, L. (2021) European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20). EFEHR Technical Report 002 V1.0.0, <https://doi.org/10.7414/EUC-EFEHR-TR002-ESRM20>.
- Danciu, L., Nandan, S., Reyes, C., Basili, R., Weatherill, G., Beauval, C., Rovida, A., Vilanova, S., Sesetyan, K., Bard, P-Y., Cotton, F., Wiemer, S., Giardini, D. (2021a) The 2020 update of the European Seismic Hazard Model: Model Overview. EFEHR Technical Report 001, v1.0.0, <https://doi.org/10.12686/a15>
- EAK (2000). Greek Seismic Code, Athens, Greece, (in Greek), with an amendment in 2003.
- FEMA P-1050-1/2015 Edition. (2015). NEHRP Recommended seismic provisions for new buildings and other structures. Building Seismic Safety Council, I, 515.
- Giardini, D., Woessner, J., Danciu, L., Crowley, H., Cotton, F., Grünthal, G., ... Rovida, A. (2013). Seismic Hazard Harmonization in Europe (SHARE): Online Data Resource. <https://doi.org/10.12686/SED-00000001-SHARE>
- Jenks, George F. (1967). The Data Model Concept in Statistical Mapping, *International Yearbook of Cartography* 7: 186–190
- Meletti, C., Marzocchi, W., D'amico, V., Lanzano, G., Luzi, L., Martinelli, F., Pace, B., Rovida, A., Taroni, M., Visini, F., Akinci, A., Anzidei, M., Avallone, A., Azzaro, R., Barani, S., Barberi, G., Barreca, G., Basili, R., Bird, P., ... Seno, S. (2021). The new Italian seismic hazard model (MPS19). *Annals of Geophysics*, 64(1). <https://doi.org/10.4401/ag-8579>
- NEAK (1992). New Seismic Greek Code. Earthquake Planning and Protection Organization, Athens, Greece
- NTC (2018). Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni NTC18, Ministerial Decree 17/01/2018, Italian Official Gazette, 42, 20 February 2018.
- Petersen, M. D., Shumway, A. M., Powers, P. M., Mueller, C. S., Moschetti, M. P., Frankel, A. D., Rezaeian, S., McNamara, D. E., Luco, N., Boyd, O. S., Rukstales, K. S., Jaiswal, K. S., Thompson, E. M., Hoover, S. M., Clayton, B. S., Field, E. H., & Zeng, Y. (2020). The 2018 update of the US National Seismic Hazard Model: Overview of model and implications. *Earthquake Spectra*, 36(1), 5–41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/8755293019878199>
- Roussopoulos, A. (1956). *Antiseismic Structures*, V. Papaxrisanthemou Publ., 2nd, Athens, 431pp.

- Woessner J, Danciu L, Giardini D, Crowley H, Cotton F, Grünthal G, Valensise G, Arvidsson R, Basili R, Demircioglu MB, Hiemer S, Meletti C, Musson RMW, Rovida AN, Sesetyan K, Stucchi M, The SHARE Consortium (2015): The 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model: Key Components and Results, *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 13 (12), 3553–3596.